

Table 2. Agronomic characters of promising rice hybrids. CLRR1, Omon, Vietnam, 1993 DS.

Hybrid	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Spikelet Sterility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R	105	98	15.3	74	31	26
IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	105	101	11.9	74	36	26
IR58025 A/IR532358-90-3-3 R	109	107	10.6	91	29	26
OM90-9 (check)	112	106	12.1	68	26	25

Kamini: a quality rice released in Bihar, India

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In areas of Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal, high-quality scented rice varieties are cultivated for use in specialty foods. Their price is at least 2-3 times more than that of ordinary varieties.

There are many tall, photoperiod-sensitive, high-quality scented varieties grown around the region. They have short, fine grains and excellent cooking quality. Popular variety Sugandha, released in the 1980s, has become highly susceptible to blast (B1) and bacterial blight (BB). To identify high-yielding varieties to replace

Sugandha, all available land races were collected, purified, and tested in varietal trials.

One of these is Katarni, which is grown intensively in the Bhagalpur division of Bihar. SBR 80-643-14-1-1, one of the six ecotypes of Katarni, yielded more than checks and was released as Kamini.

During 5 yr of yield trials, Kamini averaged 2.9 t/ha, compared with 2.5 t/ha for check Sugandha (see table). Growers highly preferred Kamini to other varieties.

Kamini is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and tolerant of brown spot, B1, and BB. It has excellent aroma and cooking quality, especially for *palao*, a specialty rice food. It is a late aman (Jun/Jul-Dec) season variety suitable for rainfed lowland conditions of Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh. ■

Performance of SBR80-643-14-1-1 in uniform variety trials, Bihar, India, 1985-89.

Year	Entry	Yield (t/ha)				
		Sabour	Tiloundha	Patna	Pusa	Av
1985	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.4	2.6	3.0	2.1	2.6
	BR9	1.3	2.4	2.0	1.5	1.9
	Sugandha	1.5	3.4	2.0	2.0	2.2
	LSD	450	402	706	591	
	CV (%)	15.8	11.7	25.6	16.1	
1986	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.0	-	3.3	2.6	2.6
	BR9	1.3	-	3.3	1.9	2.1
	Sugandha	1.1	-	2.8	2.5	2.1
	LSD	323		350		
	CV (%)	13.9		14.5		
1987	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.9	-	3.4	-	3.1
	BR9	-	-	-	-	-
	Sugandha	2.6	-	2.5	-	2.5
	LSD	412	-	460	-	
	CV (%)	9.4		12.6		
1988	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.8	-	4.2	-	3.5
	BR9	1.9	-	2.6	-	2.2
	Sugandha	2.6	-	4.0	-	3.3
	LSD	470		380		
	CV (%)	11.6		15.6		
1989	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.7	-	2.4	-	2.7
	BR9	1.9	-	-	-	1.9
	Sugandha	2.2	-	2.3	-	2.2
	LSD	354		218		
	CV (%)	10.2		12.1		

Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15: a high-quality variety in Hunan, China

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Semidwarf 86-70 (selected from IR19274-26-2-3-1-2) is a long-grained, high-quality, high-yielding variety with multiple pest resistances and wide adaptability. 86-70 was released as Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 in Hunan Province in March 1993.

The variety has an average growth duration of about 118 d. Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 performed well in 1990-91 regional trials in early rice areas. Average grain yield was 6.4 t/ha.

Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 has grain length of 7.5 mm, 3.8 L-W ratio, 1.8% average chalkiness score, high translucency, 69 mm gel consistency, alkali spreading value of 7, 19.6% average amylose content, and 9.3% protein content. Cooked grain is soft and tastes good.

Hunan soft rice is the trade name of Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15. This variety won the Golden Prize at the First Agricultural Product Exhibition of China in Oct 1992. Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 was grown on 30,000-40,000 ha in Hunan Province in 1992 and is spreading quickly in Hubei, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, and Fujian provinces. ■

Performance of IRR1 rice hybrids at Rice Research Institute (RRI), Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Pakistan

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Twenty-one hybrids using CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A were evaluated at RRI with local checks KS282 and IR6. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications conducted during 1992 kharif (monsoon) season. We transplanted 35-d-old seedlings on 15 Jul 92. Net plot size was 2 × 6.25 m² with a plant-to-plant distance of 23 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 100-50-0 kg NPK/ha. Recommended plant protection measures were adopted. We randomly selected 15